

Figure 1 Rapto de Perséfone de Bernini, drawn by Campo Baeza. The text states: "Pluto's hand on Persephone". Notebook P03 (available at the ETSAM-UPM Library)

FROM SIGNIFIER TO SIGNIFIED: UTILITAS, FIRMITAS AND VENUSTAS.

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The architectural language of Alberto Campo Baeza.

While working on my doctoral thesis on Alberto Campo Baeza's design for the headquarters of the Caja Granada Savings Bank, I have had the good fortune to study a great deal of material that the architect has published over the years.

Something that could possibly go unnoticed, but which is omnipresent in Campo Baeza's notebooks is his remarkably comprehensive outlook, revealed in so many of his notes: alongside the drawings of projects in progress one finds not only other architectural references, but also scores of notes on the music he listens to and marvels at, on sculpture, on poetry... such an immense variety of thoughts that make up the inner world from which he produces his architecture. Indeed, when talking about Beauty, Alberto Campo Baeza never discusses architecture in isolation. In his acceptance speech to the Royal Academy of Fine Arts of San Fernando, he invoked the wisdom of Saint Augustine, Cervantes, Bernini, Goya, Goethe... María Zambrano, Xavier Zubiri... Philosophers, writers, painters...

Of course, Mies Van der Rohe, Le Corbusier and Frank Lloyd Wright all have their place in the master class. And Melnikov, and Barragán too.

Nevertheless, the architect never forgets the reality of architecture: its origin and ultimate goal is to satisfy a range of uses, creating habitable spaces for human beings:

But neither the poet nor the musician nor the painter, nor almost any other creators have to fight against the laws of gravity as architects do. Neither the

work of poets, musicians or painters can fall down. Nor, like architects, do they create for reasons of necessity.¹

So what is the path from necessity to beauty? It would seem that the eternal question of architecture is not merely a mathematical formula. For as long as humankind has been in existence, humans have produced architecture, and this question has remained a constant: the role of *utilitas*, which becomes so important that it seems to eclipse *venustas*. Campo Baeza takes up the challenge:

To design is to give a unified response to a multitude of questions. To design is to give a simple answer to a complex question. It is to adopt a decision from diverse possibilities. To design is to generate an idea that when materialized, when formalized, is capable of solving all the questions raised.

In order to design one needs to know the problem well, to recognize it, and to know how it has been resolved throughout history, so as not to reinvent the wheel. It involves knowing the place well, being cognizant of the conditions and the requirements, the existing conditions and the wishes of the person commissioning the assignment, being familiar with the new technologies that make it possible to find new solutions.²

The key word at the end of this quote is technology. Construction. The tools the architect uses are the different possibilities that technology provides him with: what brushes are to the painter, and chisel and hammer are to the sculptor. *Firmitas* shows him the way. On the other hand, Campo Baeza's words reveal an open-minded attitude, especially when he stresses the need to study the problems, "*so as not to reinvent the wheel*". This is an approach he shares with a master as significant for him as Mies Van

1 Campo Baeza, Alberto. "Project design is research. There are countless reasons that demonstrate why an architectural project is a work of research" *Sharpening the scalpel* (Madrid, 2019)

2 Ibid

der Rohe, who in the following excerpt discusses the use of materials in architecture:

Therefore let us guide our students over the road of discipline from materials, through function, to creative work. Let us lead them into the healthy world of primitive building methods, where there was a meaning in every stroke of an axe, expression in every bite of a chisel.

[...] What better examples could there be for young architects? Where else could they learn such simple and true crafts than from these unknown masters?³

In this text, Mies speaks of utilizing the most primitive methods, which he intends to harness when using modern materials, mainly steel and concrete. He proposes developing a language for these materials based on the possibilities they offer and refers to an attitude based on realism.

Figure 2 Drawing of Notre Dame de Ronchamp, *in situ*. The text states: "Ave Verum Mozart. Ronchamp. And I wept uncontrollably". Notebook G05 (available at the ETSAM-UPM Library)

3 Van der Rohe, Mies. "Inaugural Address as Director of the Architecture Section of the Armour Institute of Technology". In Johnson, Philip C. *Mies Van Der Rohe*. (The Museum of Modern Art, 1947)

On the other hand, when talking about materials, we are talking about *what* they build: the whole supported by a structure. It seems appropriate, in this context, to recall the words of Alejandro de la Sota, which Campo Baeza himself quotes:

And he suggested us to imagine a woman that would give birth to a baby and she would realize that it was born without skeleton. And that the doctor would be called to open the baby and introduce a skeleton. Well, this way some architects, wrongly, behave. They invent forms and, afterwards, they call the doctor, the engineer, to insert a skeleton, a structure. The structure, the skeleton, in the human being and in the architectural space, must be present from the first moment of conception.⁴

Figure 3 Drawing of the process at the Caja Granada Savings Bank. The text states: "After reading *The Death of the Lion* by Henry James (fantastic)". Notebook G03 (available at the ETSAM-UPM Library)

4 Campo Baeza, Alberto. "Project design is research" *Sharpening the scalpel* (Madrid, 2019)

For Campo Baeza, *utilitas* and *firmitas* represent a question with an intrinsic logic: the uses are arranged rationally, and the materials have specific possibilities. And in his architecture he manages to harmonise them by mastering dimensions:

The geometry that defines the lines of the structure in Campo Baeza's architecture is an encompassing geometry, one that gets the most –dimension– out of the place, the function and the budget.⁵

But at this point, it seems that without *venustas*, the builder would have done his job.

When we talk about Beauty, all agree that it is something that transcends, that surpasses our usual modes of reasoning. And although this is partly the case, there is a risk of detaching Beauty from rational discourse. The risk of giving space to the absence of logic or the knowledge that an architect, as a professional, needs. So, after extolling Beauty as hugely significant, one could end up considering it as something superfluous. At this juncture we need to go back to the early times:

The architect should be equipped with knowledge of many branches of study and varied kinds of learning, for it is by his judgement that all work done by the other arts is put to test. This knowledge is the child of practice and theory.

[...] those who have a thorough knowledge of both, like men armed at all points, have the sooner attained their object and carried authority with them. In all matters, but particularly in architecture, there are these two points:—the thing signified, and that which gives it its significance. That which is signified is the subject of which we may be speaking; and that which gives significance is a demonstration on scientific principles. It appears, then, that one who professes himself an architect should be well versed in both directions.⁶

5 Aparicio Guisado, Jesús. "The Alchemist of Space". www.campobaeza.com. (June, 2021)

6 Vitruvius, Marcus Pollio. *Los Diez Libros de Arquitectura* (Barcelona: Obras Maestras, Editorial Iberia)

Knowledge and studies. The thing signified, and that which gives it its significance, the object of study and the method of approaching it.

Him I call an architect who, by an admirable and intelligent theory and method is able to devise with thought and invention and to complete through execution by means of the movement of great weights and the conjunction and amassment of bodies, all those works which can, with the greatest beauty, be adapted to the uses of mankind: and to be able to do this he must have thorough insight into the noblest and most curious sciences.⁷

Here Alberti is more specific than Vitruvius and he points out that this knowledge, that which gives significance in architecture, is the method of arranging the weights, of joining and assembling the bodies. In short: the signifier is the word, the language of construction.

Figure 4 Cross-section of the Orihuela Public Library. Campo Baeza presented this work as a research project in the competitive exams for the university chair which he was awarded.

7 Battista Alberti, Leone. *De Re Aedificatoria*.

That which is signified: the needs of human beings, which have to be satisfied in the most beautiful way. Because for Renaissance man, transcendental Beauty is not simply an option: it is as necessary as the conditions for human habitation. That is why the architect needs the intellect and knowledge of ‘the noblest and most curious sciences’.

But, what about today’s world?

Let Melnikov, the architect so admired by Campo Baeza, supply the key to rescuing *venustas*: “A soul is hidden in the structure of the building. Knowing how to awaken it means creating architecture”.⁸

That soul that Melnikov speaks of is the one that is the cross-cutting link: it is *venustas* that calls out to the human being. And for architects today, who have almost unlimited technologies at their disposal, handling this language in a beautiful way is the path to *Venustas*. Just as we make poetry out of the beautiful use of spoken language, we can make architecture out of the “language of construction”. Now and forever: the fact that language is involving is not an impediment, because the need for Beauty remains.

In fact, Mies Van der Rohe supports this viewpoint:

Yet the achievements of pure technology still challenge architects to meet the spiritual needs of men in an equally convincing way. For architecture depends on facts, but its real field of activity lies in the realm of significance.⁹

Signifier and signified. Clear and distinct. Without formal excesses, from the beautiful use of language, we achieve Beauty. We achieve *venustas*. And the German architect also states:

8 Konstantin Melnikov, quotation cited by Strigalev, Kokkinaki. *Melnikov en París: del pabellón soviético a los garajes*. 2004. Doctoral thesis by Garrido Colmenero, Ginés Ignacio. Architecture. ETSAM-UPM. p.399.

9 Van der Rohe, Mies, quote in: Osborn, Robert. “The Evolution of the Craftsman?” *Perspecta* 3 (1955).

I want a structural architecture, because I believe that is the only way by which we can have a communion with the essentials of our civilization.¹⁰

Campo Baeza has, in fact, turned his structural language into his trademark. He has been able to develop a use of language which, although personal, aspires to this very essential and universal nature.

What is signified at the center of his discourse is, as we know, the light-gravity binomial. Language is formulated in two types of structure that express this: stereotomic and tectonic. This is how the architect himself explains it:

We could initially read these four projects in the light of concepts of the stereotomic and the tectonic in architecture. As if we were using a camera, we'll adjust the settings of our analysis to have a stereotomic aperture and a tectonic shutter speed. Isn't architecture also simply a matter of determining light and distance in relation to man? These two terms, taken from Gottfried Semper by way of Kenneth Frampton, have been effective instruments for me in developing a more precise architecture.

We understand stereotomic architecture to be that in which gravity is transmitted continuously, in a continuous structural system where the construction has complete continuity.

It is massive, stony, weighty architecture, which sits on the earth as if born from within it. It is architecture that seeks light, that perforates its walls so that light may enter. It is the architecture of the podium, the plinth and the stylobate. It is, in short, the architecture of a cave.

We understand tectonic architecture to be that in which gravity is transmitted discontinuously in a knotted structural system with a syncopated construction. It is bony, woody, light architecture, which rests on the earth as if it were standing on tiptoes. It is architecture that defends itself from light, which has

10 Van der Rohe, Mies. "No Dogma" *Interbuild* 6 (June 1959)

to place veils over its openings in order to control the light flooding in. It is architecture of the shell, of the abacus. It is, in short, the architecture of a hut.¹¹

Campo Baeza carves out a route that has characterized all his architectural work. He creates a language capable of satisfying and expressing function. *Firmitas* that expresses *utilitas*. *Firmitas* that, through its virtuous use, is *venustas*.

Figure 5 Interior view of the Caja Granada Savings Bank. It was the turning point in his career, marking initial signs of interest in the tectonic-stereotomic duality in his architecture

11 Campo Baeza, Alberto. "BOXES, LITTLE BOXES, BIG BOXES. From the Stereotomic to the Tectonic" *The Built Idea* (Oscar Riera Ojeda Publishers, 2011)

This is how Jesús Aparicio describes it:

Alberto Campo Baeza casts a double gaze that can be distinguished in each one of his works: that on function and that on place. In both cases, his is a gaze in which intellectual abstraction is wisely combined with sensory experience. This dual vision is incorporated in the perception of the spaces he builds, spaces whose center is always man, the human being in whom are combined, as in Leonardo's Vitruvian Man, universality, geometry, proportion and particularity.¹²

Figure 6 Ground plan and cross-section study of the BIT Centre in Mallorca. It represents the pinnacle of Campo Baeza's research into tectonic-stereotomic duality.

12 Aparicio Guisado, Jesús. "The Alchemist of Space". www.campobaeza.com. (June, 2021)